

1 **Granulation and microbial community dynamics in the**
2 **chitosan-supplemented anaerobic treatment of**
3 **wastewater polluted with organic solvents**

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23 **Abstract**

24 The effect of chitosan on the development of granular sludge in upflow anaerobic
25 sludge blanket reactors (UASB) when treating wastewater polluted with the organic
26 solvents ethanol, ethyl acetate, and 1-ethoxy-2-propanol was evaluated. Three UASB
27 reactors were operated for 219 days at ambient temperature with an organic loading rate
28 (OLR) of between $0.3 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $20 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$. One reactor was operated
29 without the addition of chitosan, while the other two were operated with the addition of
30 chitosan doses of 2.4 mg gVSS^{-1} two times. The three reactors were all able to treat the
31 OLR tested with COD removal efficiencies greater than 90%. However, the time
32 required to reach stable operation was considerably reduced in the chitosan-assisted
33 reactors. The development of granules in the reactors with chitosan was accelerated and
34 granules larger than $2000 \mu\text{m}$ were only observed in these reactors. In addition, these
35 granules exhibited better physiochemical characteristics: the mean particle diameter
36 (540 and $613 \mu\text{m}$) was approximately two times greater than in the control reactor (300
37 μm), and the settling velocities exceeded 35 m h^{-1} . The extracellular polymeric
38 substances (EPS) in the reactors with the chitosan was found to be higher than in the
39 control reactor. The protein-EPS content has been correlated with the granule size. The
40 analyses of the microbial communities, performed through denaturing gradient gel
41 electrophoresis and high-throughput sequencing, revealed that the syntrophic
42 microorganism belonging to genus *Geobacter* and the hydrogenotrophic methanogen
43 *Methanocorpusculum labreanum* were predominant in the granules. Other methanogens
44 like *Methanosaeta* species were found earlier in the chitosan-assisted reactors than in
45 the control reactor.

46 **Keywords:** Chitosan, DGGE, Granulation, High-throughput sequencing, Solvents,
47 UASB

48 **1 Introduction**

49 Interest in the biological treatment of industrial wastewater has increased in recent
50 decades due to the increased pollution of water resources and its implications for human
51 health. Among the industrial sectors, those that use organic solvents in the production of
52 paints, adhesives, rubber, pharmaceutical and petroleum products, among others, can
53 generate large quantities of solvent polluted wastewater (Dzikowitzky and
54 Schwarzbauer, 2013; Oktem et al., 2007). Organic solvents are flammable, malodorous
55 and potentially toxic to aquatic ecosystems and thus require complete elimination by
56 wastewater treatment (Henry et al., 1996). As suitable biological wastewater treatments,
57 the anaerobic processes have shown advantages including energy recovery as biogas
58 and lower energy costs (van Lier, 2008). The high rate sludge bed reactors such as the
59 Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket reactor (UASB) and its derivatives are by far, the
60 most popular anaerobic systems for the treatment of industrial wastewater because they
61 achieve high biomass retention improving the treatment efficiency while applying high
62 loading rates (van Lier et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2006). Recently, this type of reactor has
63 been successfully applied to the treatment of wastewater polluted with organic solvents
64 (Bravo et al., 2017; Enright et al., 2009; Lafita et al., 2015; Oktem et al., 2007; Siggins
65 et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2017).

66 The success of the operation of sludge bed anaerobic reactors lies in the formation and
67 stability of granules. Granulation is the result of the self-immobilization of anaerobic
68 microorganisms under certain physicochemical and biological conditions. Although
69 granule formation has been widely studied, this phenomenon occurs within a limited
70 range of wastewater characteristics and reactor designs (Uyanik et al., 2002) since the
71 microstructure of the granules may be affected by the complexity of the substrate (Liu et
72 al., 2002). The extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) play an important role in

73 granulation because they can bind cells closely through ion binding interactions,
74 hydrophobic interactions, and polymer entanglement (Sheng et al., 2010). The EPS that
75 result from cell secretions, cellular lysis and hydrolysis of macromolecules mainly
76 contains polysaccharides, proteins, nucleic acids, lipids, uronic acids and humic
77 substances, although its production and composition may be affected by the wastewater
78 type. For example, Schmidt and Ahring (1994) indicated that the production of EPS was
79 limited in granules grown on acetogenic and methanogenic substrates in comparison to
80 more complex wastewaters, and Fukuzaki et al. (1995) observed greater amounts of
81 EPS in granules grown in starch or sucrose than in ethanol or butyrate-propionate.
82 These observations could indicate that granules are less likely to develop in the solvent
83 polluted wastewaters. Moreover, some researchers have reported the disintegration of
84 granules when treating mixtures containing organic oxygenated solvents (Lafita et al.,
85 2015; Lu et al., 2015). Therefore, it has become necessary to study the granulation that
86 occurs when treating industrial wastewater polluted with solvents in order to evaluate
87 granule stability and the robustness of the operation. Researchers have already studied
88 granule formation in the treatment of wastewater polluted with phenol (Ramakrishnan
89 and Gupta, 2006), by natural rubber processing (Thanh et al., 2016), or from the kraft
90 pulp industry (Lu et al., 2017).

91 The addition of cationic polymers to high rate anaerobic reactors enhances the
92 granulation process resulting in faster granule development (Show et al., 2004). Among
93 these cationic polymers, chitosan stands out for its availability, environmental
94 friendliness, and biodegradability (Yang et al., 2016). Although chitosan has not been
95 proven for its granulation effect in wastewater containing solvents, a few studies have
96 pointed to the beneficial effect of this biopolymer when used with other substrates. El-
97 Mamouni et al. (1998) reported that the granulation rate in UASB reactors fed with

98 sucrose was 2.5 times higher in the reactor containing chitosan than in the control
99 reactor. Hudayah et al. (2016) found that in the treatment of wastewater containing
100 glucose and volatile fatty acids (VFA) as substrates, the addition of chitosan increased
101 the average diameter size of the granules by 115 μm .

102 Anaerobic granulation is a complex process in which not only physical but also
103 biological and microbiological factors are involved (Hulshoff Pol et al., 2004).
104 Knowledge of the microbial community implicated in the granulation of sludge that is
105 fed with a specific substrate is essential, because it makes possible an elucidation of the
106 potential capacities and limitations of the granules. In turn, these determine the
107 performance and feasibility of the operation. Thus, methanogens related to the
108 *Methanosaeta* species have been reported to be key microorganisms in anaerobic
109 aggregation (Gagliano et al., 2017; Hulshoff Pol et al., 2004; Wiegant, 1987). In
110 reactors in which high acetate concentrations in the effluent are maintained,
111 *Methanosarcina* species became the dominant aceticlastic methanogens because they
112 may resist to VFA inhibition by forming multicellular aggregates in which the VFA
113 concentrations are limited by a slow diffusion rate (Vavilin et al., 2008). Other
114 researchers have found that *Methanomicrobiales* play a critical role in the formation of
115 granules at low temperature (O'Reilly et al., 2010). The presence and abundance of
116 specific microorganisms in granular sludge depends on the type of substrate and on the
117 operational and environmental conditions of the process, but few studies are to be found
118 on the evolution of the microbial community during the granulation process in the
119 treatment of wastewater containing organic solvents.

120 The present study aims to evaluate granulation and the dynamics of the microbial
121 community in anaerobic reactors treating a mixture of oxygenated organic solvents
122 when chitosan is added to assist the granulation process. To this end, three UASB

123 reactors fed with wastewater polluted with ethanol, ethyl acetate and 1-ethoxy-2-
124 propanol, as the major constituents of the emission from the flexographic industry, were
125 operated at ambient temperature for more than 200 days. The addition of chitosan was
126 evaluated for its effect both on the system performance and on the granulation process.
127 The dynamics of the physicochemical characteristics of granules, such as particle size
128 and extracellular polymer production, were examined. To gain insight into the
129 microbiology of the process, the evolution of the microbial community was evaluated
130 throughout the experiment by the use of molecular biology techniques.

131

132 **2 Materials and methods**

133 2.1 UASB reactors and operation

134 2.1.1 *Experimental set-up*

135 The experiments were carried out in three UASB reactors (R1, R2 and R3) for which a
136 schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 1. The reactors consisted of two PVC parts: a
137 bottom zone of 6.5 cm in diameter and 120 cm in height, and a settling zone containing
138 the gas-liquid-solid (GLS) separator, with a diameter of 20 cm and a height of 24 cm for
139 R1 and R2 (effective volume of 7.8 L) and 12 cm for R3 (effective volume of 4.5 L).
140 The reactors were fed with wastewater contaminated with a mixture of ethanol, ethyl
141 acetate and 1-ethoxy-2 propanol (E2P), with a mass ratio of 7:2:1, by using a syringe
142 pump (New Era, 1000 model, USA). The influent was supplemented with NaHCO₃ so
143 as to maintain the reactor pH between 7 and 7.5, the macronutrients in a COD:N:P ratio
144 of 300:2:1, Ca⁺² and Mg⁺² to ensure 150 and 40 mg L⁻¹ respectively, and micronutrients
145 (Table Sup1). The up-flow velocity was adjusted, if necessary, by effluent recirculation

146 using a peristaltic pump (Watson-Marlow, USA). Biogas produced was passed through
147 a NaOH solution to allow CO₂ absorption before being conducted to the volumetric
148 drum-type gas flow meter MilliGascounter (Ritter TG 05, Germany).

149 2.1.2 *Inoculum*

150 Sludge collected from the anaerobic digester of the Quart-Benager municipal
151 wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) located in Valencia (Spain) was used as the
152 inoculum. The sludge had a total suspended solids (TSS) concentration of 24.6 g L⁻¹
153 with a volatile suspended solids (VSS) content of 63%, a mean particle size of 63.7 μm
154 and specific methanogenic activity (SMA) of 8.2 Nml CH₄ g VSS⁻¹ d⁻¹ for the mixture
155 of solvents in this study.

156 2.1.3 *Experimental procedure*

157 The three reactors (R1, R2 and R3) were seeded with 2.5 L of inoculum and then
158 operated at room temperature for the whole experiment (24.0 ± 1.4°C, suboptimal
159 mesophilic temperature). R1 was operated as the control reactor without the addition of
160 chitosan; whereas R2 and R3 were supplied with a single dose of 2.4 mg g VSS⁻¹ of
161 chitosan together with the inoculum during the seeding. Chitosan was added to the
162 reactors using a stock solution of 10 g L⁻¹ of commercial grade chitosan powder -
163 medium molecular weight and deacetylation grade of 75% (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain)- in
164 1% acetic acid. The optimal chitosan dose was determined from a flocculation test (Fig.
165 Sup1). The granulation experiment was divided into three phases and the operational
166 parameters are summarized in Table 1. For more detail, Fig. Sup2 shows the changes of
167 the operational parameters over time in all reactors. During phase I (days 0 to 22),
168 considered the adaptation period for the organic solvents, the organic loading rate
169 (OLR) was increased from 0.3 to 0.6 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹ at a hydraulic retention time

170 (HRT) of 7.8 d. R1 and R2 were operated with recirculation, setting the up-flow
171 velocity at 1 m h^{-1} . R3 was operated without recirculation. On day 23, at the beginning
172 of phase II (days 23 to 89), a second dose of $2.4 \text{ mg g VSS}^{-1}$ of chitosan was supplied to
173 R2 and R3. A load of 18 g COD d^{-1} was then applied, corresponding to an OLR of 2.3
174 $\text{kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for R1 and R2, and $4 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for R3. In this phase, the up-flow
175 velocity was kept at the same value as during the previous stage. From day 90 to day
176 219 (phase III), the recirculation was switched off in R1 and R2 in the light of results
177 obtained in phase II. The OLR was gradually increased in a stepwise fashion up to 20
178 $\text{kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$. The OLR steps were performed by shortening the HRT or by increasing
179 the load of solvents after achieving a stable performance at each OLR step (considered
180 as variations of less than 5% in the COD removal efficiency for a period lasting at least
181 3 times the HRT, and VFA concentration in the effluent below $150 \text{ mg HAc L}^{-1}$).

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183 2.2 Properties of the granules

184 2.2.1 Particle size distribution, settling velocity and morphology

185 Particle size distribution on a volume basis was measured every 4–5 weeks by laser
186 diffraction using a Mastersizer 2000 (Malvern Instruments Ltd, UK) with a detection
187 range of $0.02\text{--}2000 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The sludge samples were taken from each reactor and filtered
188 through a 2 mm sieve to determine the quantity of particles with a diameter $>2 \text{ mm}$. The
189 fraction $<2 \text{ mm}$ was measured in the Mastersizer 2000 in triplicate. The settling velocity
190 was determined according to the method proposed by Ghangrekar et al. (2005) using a
191 60 cm height PVC column with a 6 cm diameter. In addition, the morphology of the
192 granules was analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM-4100 model, Hitachi,

193 Japan). Previously, the granules samples were fixed, dried to the critical point and
194 sputter coated by Au-Pd.

195 2.2.2 *Specific Methanogenic Activity (SMA)*

196 Measurement of SMA was conducted in an automatic methane potential test system
197 (AMPTS) II (Bioprocess control, Sweden) from the biomass sampled from the reactors
198 at the end of the experiment (day 219) in order to evaluate the biodegradability of the
199 solvents in the granular sludge. The tests were carried out at 25°C in triplicate by using
200 500 mL flasks intermittently stirred (1 min on/ 1 min off) at 112 rpm. Flasks were filled
201 with biomass and medium at a ratio of 2.5 g VSS g COD⁻¹. The medium consisted of
202 synthetic wastewater contaminated with a sole solvent (ethanol, ethyl acetate, or E2P) or
203 with the mixture, with a COD concentration of 2.5 g L⁻¹, fortified with micro and
204 macro-nutrients according to Table Sup1, and buffered at pH 7–7.5 by adding NaHCO₃.
205 Methane was monitored in the gas meter device, the CO₂ having been previously
206 removed by passing through a NaOH 3M solution. The SMA was evaluated as the
207 maximum specific methane production rate (Loosdrecht et al., 2016).

208 2.2.3 *Extraction and characterization of EPS*

209 The EPS of granules sampled for particle size distribution was extracted by using the
210 method proposed by Frølund et al. (1996) and modified by D'Abzac et al. (2010) using
211 a cationic exchange resin (Dowex 20–50 mesh, Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) at a ratio of 70 g
212 resin g VSS⁻¹. The polysaccharides and proteins were determined by the colorimetric
213 methods proposed by Dubois et al. (1956) and Lowry et al. (1951), respectively.

214 2.3 Analytical methods

215 Soluble COD of samples filtered by 0.22 μm , TSS and VSS were measured twice per
216 week according to Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater
217 (APHA, 1998). VFA and alkalinity of centrifuged samples were daily determined
218 according to the 5-point acid-base titration method described by Moosbrugger et al.
219 (1992), using a titrator (848 Titrino Plus, Metrohm, Switzerland). The VFA represents
220 the concentration of short chain volatile fatty acids, expressed as acetic acid (mg HAc L^{-1})
221 ¹). Effluent solvent content of samples filtered by 0.22 μm was analyzed twice per week
222 by gas chromatography (Agilent GC 7890A, Spain) equipped with a Restek Rtx-VMS
223 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 1.4 μm) with helium at a flow-rate of 1.3 mL min^{-1} and a
224 flame ionization detector (FID). The injector and detector temperatures were 190°C and
225 240°C, respectively, and oven temperature ramp was used: 60°C for 14 min and then
226 25°C min^{-1} to 110°C. Methane production for each reactor was monitored by the gas
227 meter MilliGascounter (Ritter TG 05, Germany). Biogas composition was analyzed
228 using an Agilent gas chromatograph (7820A) with thermal conductivity detector (TCD).
229 0.5 mL of biogas (before CO_2 absorption) was separated into two columns connected in
230 series: HP-Plot/U (30 m x 0.32 mm x 10 μm) and HP-Molisieve (30 m x 0.32 mm x 12
231 μm), by using helium as a carrier at a flow-rate of 4.2 mL min^{-1} . The injector, oven and
232 detector temperatures were 200°C, 40°C and 250°C, respectively.

233 2.4 Microbial community analysis

234 Sludge samples were taken from the three reactors on days 0, 37, 89, 131, and 169.
235 DNA was extracted from 0.5 g of sludge using a FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil Isolation
236 (MP Biomedicals, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions and stored at -20°C.
237 The bacterial and archaeal 16S rRNA were amplified by PCR using the primers

238 proposed by Bravo et al. (2017) under the following conditions: 94°C for 5 min, 19
239 cycles at 94°C for 1 min, 65°C for 0.5 min and 72°C for 1 min, followed by 12 cycles
240 for bacteria and 16 cycles for archaea of 94°C for 1 min, 55°C for 0.5 min, 72°C for 1
241 min, and a final extension step at 72°C for 10 min. Denaturing gradient gel
242 electrophoresis (DGGE) analysis, subsequent band excision, purification and
243 sequencing were done by adapting the method used by Bravo et al. (2017). In this work,
244 a linear denaturant gradient from 25% to 60% was used and electrophoresis was
245 performed at 60°C and 100 V for 14 h. The V4 hyper-variable region of the extracted
246 DNA was amplified with the universal primers 515F (5'-GTG CCA GCM GCC GCG
247 GTA A-3') and 806R (5'-GGA CTA CHV GGG TWT CTA AT-3'). Sequencing was
248 performed using a MiSeq System (Illumina, USA). Raw 16S rRNA gene sequences
249 obtained were screened and trimmed by using the Quantitative Insights Into Microbial
250 Ecology (QIIME) software with a sequence length (200 nt) and mean quality score cut-
251 off of (25nt).

252 **3 Results and discussion**

253 3.1 Performance of the UASB reactors

254 The performance of the three reactors in terms of COD removal efficiency (RE_{COD} ,
255 defined in supplementary section) and the variation of the effluent VFA concentration
256 are shown in Fig. 2a and 2b, respectively. After inoculation, RE_{COD} were 77, 88 and
257 90% in the control reactor (R1), R2 and R3, respectively (Fig. 2a). During phase I, the
258 reactors with chitosan (R2 and R3) exhibited faster adaptation to solvents with RE_{COD}
259 higher than 92% from day 11 onwards, whereas R1 achieved a value of 84% on day 22.
260 The VFA concentration evolution also showed better performance in the reactors with
261 chitosan (Fig. 2b): Values were lower than 75 mg HAc L⁻¹ after nine days, and no VFA

262 was detected by the end of this phase. In R1, the VFA concentration values remained
263 between 228 and 389 mg HAc L⁻¹.

264 Phase II started on day 23 with a second dose of chitosan and an OLR increase. The
265 RE_{COD} in R1 decreased to 75% in response to the OLR increase then gradually
266 increased up to 97% towards the end of this phase according to the decrease in the VFA
267 concentration. In contrast, R2 and R3 showed stable RE_{COD} values (93 to 99%) and
268 lower VFA concentrations in the effluent than R1. The control reactor took 57 days to
269 achieve removal efficiencies higher than 92%, whereas R2 and R3 took only 11 days.
270 The results of these two phases indicated that two doses of chitosan improved the
271 acclimatization period of a flocculent sludge when treating organic solvents in UASB
272 reactors. Show et al. (2004) observed similar effect in UASB reactors fed with peptone-
273 glucose wastewater, where the addition of a single dose of a cationic polymer at a
274 concentration of 80 mg L⁻¹ accelerated the start-up time. The enhancement in the start-
275 up could be explained by the earlier formation of aggregates in the chitosan-assisted
276 reactors as it will be discussed in the next section.

277 During phase III (days 90 to 219), operational conditions were changed to promote the
278 development of granules. Step increases in the OLR of up to 20 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹ were
279 performed in each reactor according to its response. The increase in the OLR usually
280 resulted in an initial decrease in RE_{COD}; however, during stable performance at each
281 OLR step, each reactor reached a value higher than 90%, thereby demonstrating high
282 capacity to treat the solvents. Differences were observed in the performance of the three
283 reactors. For example, R1 and R2 needed 24 days to achieve a stable performance at an
284 OLR of 5 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹. During these 24 days, R3 was able to treat up to 10.5 kg
285 COD m⁻³ d⁻¹ with an average RE_{COD} of 98%. The VFA concentration in R1 initially
286 reached 360 mg HAc L⁻¹ and decreased to 69 mg HAc L⁻¹ before the next OLR step was

287 applied. The VFA concentrations in R2 and R3 remained below 100 mg HAc L⁻¹. The
288 next OLR step applied in R1 and R2 (on day 119) led to a decrease of the RE_{COD} and
289 higher values of VFA in the effluent of R1 (Fig. 2b). In order to avoid the failure of this
290 reactor, the OLR was decreased until operating conditions were restored with RE_{COD}
291 higher than 85%. The response to the increase in OLR in the reactors with chitosan was
292 different to that observed in the control reactor. As can be seen in Fig. 2b, R1 showed a
293 higher oscillation in VFA concentrations with an average of 176 ± 146 mg HAc L⁻¹,
294 which indicated an imbalance between acetogenesis and methanogenesis. This
295 contrasted with the chitosan-assisted reactors, where there were averages of 60 ± 63 and
296 26 ± 81 mg HAc L⁻¹ for R2 and R3, respectively. The time required to reach an OLR of
297 20 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹ was 107, 72 and 37 days for R1, R2 and R3, respectively, from the
298 beginning of the phase III. Operating at this OLR, stable RE_{COD} higher than 93% were
299 obtained for the three reactors. From day 133 to day 147, R3 operated at 25 kg COD m⁻³
300 d⁻¹; however, excessive biomass washed out (846 mg VSS L⁻¹ in the effluent) on day
301 145 and an increase of the VFA concentration was observed (Fig 2b). Therefore, the
302 OLR was gradually decreased to 20 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹.

303 The methane yield was determined for phase III fitting the methane produced and the
304 COD removed, obtaining values of 0.292±0.008, 0.323±0.004 and 0.335±0.005 Nm³
305 CH₄ kg COD_{removed}⁻¹ for R1, R2, and R3, respectively. The values from the reactors with
306 chitosan were closer to the stoichiometric value (0.35 Nm³ CH₄ kg COD_{removed}⁻¹).

307 The analysis of the solvent content in the effluent throughout the study showed that the
308 only remarkable compound detected was 1-ethoxy-2-propanol (E2P). Ethanol and ethyl
309 acetate were almost completely degraded, with their concentrations always below 10
310 ppm. Intermediate compounds such as acetone and isopropanol were also detected (<10
311 ppm). Bravo et al. (2017) hypothesized that E2P would be decomposed after enzymatic

312 ether cleavage to ethanol and acetone. This assumption is corroborated by the low
313 concentrations of acetone measured in the effluents of the reactors. The variations in the
314 E2P removal efficiency (RE_{E2P} , defined in supplementary section) according to the
315 OLR of this solvent are shown in Fig. 3. The reactors with chitosan were able to achieve
316 RE_{E2P} of 79% from day 14 onwards; while the control reactor needed 40 days to achieve
317 values of around 70%. During phase III, the control reactor showed more oscillations in
318 behavior related to E2P degradation, and at the final E2P OLR of $2 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$,
319 average removal percentages of 62 ± 8 , 70 ± 3 and 71 ± 2 were obtained in R1, R2, and R3,
320 respectively. The outcomes of the reactors' performance suggest that the addition of
321 chitosan enhances the adaptation of UASB reactors to the degradation of solvents,
322 including a complex one such as E2P, improving the overall performance and the
323 robustness of the system.

324

325 3.2 Development of granules

326 The development of granules throughout the study was evaluated from biomass samples
327 from the three reactors taken on days 0, 22, 54, 89, 112, 131, 169, 190 and 219. The
328 evolution of the particle size distribution is presented in Fig. 4. In this study, particles
329 with a diameter greater than $300 \mu\text{m}$ were considered to be granules, in the order of the
330 minimum granules diameter indicated by Bhunia and Ghangrekar (2007). Table 2
331 summarizes the percentage of granules over time in all reactors. After 22 days of
332 operation, the percentage of granules increased significantly from 0.3% to values of 3.0,
333 4.0 and 6.8% in R1, R2 and R3, respectively. After the second addition of chitosan on
334 day 23, the samples taken during phase II showed that R3, operating with chitosan and
335 without recirculation, presented a greater granulation rate; between the reactors operated

336 with recirculation, the chitosan-assisted reactor (R2) reached a percentage of granules
337 greater than that obtained in the reactor without chitosan (R1). At the end of this phase,
338 on day 89, the percentage of granules in R3 was 21.9%, while a low increase in granules
339 was observed for R1 and R2 with 4.9 and 8.5%, respectively. In addition, the samples
340 taken on this day show that the percentage of fine particles (<100 μm) in R3 decreased
341 by half, whereas that in R1 and R2 it only decreased 11 and 15%, respectively.
342 According to the granulation theory, the selection pressure created by the hydraulic and
343 gas loading rates induces the washing out of light and dispersed sludge particles, while
344 the heavier components remain in the system promoting sludge granulation (Hulshoff
345 Pol et al., 2004). However, during phase II, the sludge blanket in R1 and R2 was often
346 observed to be accumulated in the settling zone, with subsequent recirculation and low
347 washing out of fine particles with the effluent. Hence, the almost unvaried particle size
348 distribution could be the result of retaining the fine particles instead of promoting their
349 washing out. It was therefore decided that the recirculation in R1 and R2 would be
350 switched off, so that during phase III all three reactors were operated without
351 recirculation and with stepwise increases in the OLR. Under these conditions the
352 granules grew faster in the chitosan-assisted reactors, and larger granules were observed
353 in comparison to the control reactor. On day 112 (22 days after the starting of the phase
354 III) the percentage of granules in R1 did not show significant variation (4.9%), while in
355 R2 and R3 it was 22.7% and 24.5%, respectively, showing the enhancement of the
356 granulation in the chitosan-assisted reactors. From that point onwards, the percentage of
357 granules increased until values of 42.0% in R1, 54.0% in R2, and 64.7% in R3.
358 Regarding the granule size (Figure 4), granules larger than 1000 μm appeared earlier in
359 the chitosan assisted-reactors, and granules > 2000 μm were only found in these
360 reactors. At the end of the study, the mean particle diameter was significantly higher in

361 R2 and R3, with values of 540 μm and 613 μm respectively, compared with 300 μm
362 obtained in R1. The results showed that granulation was possible in all three reactors
363 when a high selection pressure was applied, which was induced by a gradual increase in
364 the organic loading rate. However, the granules formation was improved in the
365 chitosan-assisted reactors, with a consequent increase of biomass retention and of the
366 methanogenic activity in turn. Yang et al. (2016) have suggested that the main
367 mechanisms of microbial flocculation in the presence of chitosan are related to charge
368 neutralization and bridging.

369 A significant parameter in the quality of the granular sludge is its settling velocity.
370 Granules from the control reactor measured on day 219 presented a settling velocity of
371 26.4 m h^{-1} , but the granules from the reactors with chitosan, R2 and R3, exhibited better
372 settling velocities with 1.4 (36.7 m h^{-1}) and 1.8 (46.8 m h^{-1}) times higher values,
373 respectively. The fact that granules were formed earlier and with better physical
374 characteristics in the chitosan-assisted reactors could be attributed to a higher retention
375 of microorganisms inside the matrix formed by the polymer. To evaluate this
376 assumption, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained from the
377 granules on day 219. Fig. 5a and 5b show the granules formed in R1 and in R3 (R2 had
378 a similar appearance), respectively. The granules developed in all three reactors were
379 rigid and densely packed with a smooth surface. The granules from R3 showed the
380 typical EPS formations embedding diverse arrangements of microorganism (Fig. 5d),
381 whereas in R1 such EPS formations were not directly observed in the SEM images. The
382 magnification of the granules' surface showed a heterogeneous microbial community:
383 cocci, rods and filamentous microorganisms were observed, these last ones identified to
384 a greater extent in the reactors with chitosan added. *Methanosaeta* rods- (Fig 5.c) and

385 rods/filaments-like morphology (Fig 5.d) can be seen, being more abundant in the
386 chitosan-assisted reactor.

387

388 3.3 EPS Production

389 Table 3 shows the evolution of the EPS content, which involved both polysaccharides
390 and proteins, in the three UASB reactors. After the acclimation period, an increase in
391 the OLR in phase II resulted in a sharp increase to the polysaccharide-EPS content,
392 although it decreased by the end of this phase. This behavior corresponded to the
393 increase in the VFA concentration caused by the increase in the OLR, which is in
394 agreement with several studies indicating that OLR-stressful conditions promote EPS
395 production (Puñal et al., 2003; Zhou et al., 2006). Once the system became stable,
396 polysaccharide-EPS production decreased again. From day 112 on, with successive
397 increments in the OLR, the polysaccharide-EPS content of the three reactors increased,
398 although it did so to a higher extent in the reactors with added chitosan. This may be
399 related to the more rapid increases in the OLR that occurred in these reactors.

400 The protein-EPS content of R2 and R3 showed higher values than that of the control
401 reactor; the values increased in relation to the formation of granules. From day 131
402 onwards, a sharp increase in protein-EPS content was observed as larger granules
403 appeared, suggesting a correlation between the protein-EPS content and the granulation
404 process (Fig. Sup3). Zhang et al. (2007) also observed an increase of the protein-EPS
405 content as aerobic granulation occurred. These authors suggested that the increase of the
406 protein might favor the granulation by affecting the relative hydrophobicity of cell
407 surfaces and by reducing the electrostatic repulsion between cells.

408

409 3.4 Specific Methanogenic Activity (SMA)

410 At the end of the experiment, SMA assays for the granular sludge taken from the
411 three reactors were carried out using a sole solvent or the ternary mixture as substrate.
412 These results are presented in Table 4. Higher methanogenic activities were evident in
413 the sludge from the chitosan-assisted for all substrates evaluated. Similar results were
414 observed by El-Mamouni (1998). The SMA values obtained in this study were higher
415 than others reported at suboptimal mesophilic temperature when using a granular sludge
416 adapted to organic solvents. For instance, Lafita et al. (2015) reported an SMA of 214.5
417 $\text{NmL CH}_4 \text{ g VSS}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for ethanol and of 24.3 $\text{NmL CH}_4 \text{ g VSS}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for 1-methoxy-2-
418 propanol at 25°C. Ethyl acetate has been described as a readily biodegradable solvent
419 under anaerobic conditions (Henry et al., 1996). Yanti et al. (2014) suggest that the
420 mechanism of ethyl ester degradation is the same as that of methyl ester, i.e., these
421 compounds are degraded to carboxylic acids and alcohols. Following this process, ethyl
422 acetate would be transformed into acetic acid and ethanol, and it seems that this step
423 could be the kinetically limiting one because of the slightly lower values of SMA for
424 ethyl acetate than for ethanol. The SMA values obtained for E2P were significantly
425 lower (an average of 5 times) than the values observed for the other two solvents
426 (ethanol and ethyl acetate). In addition, no lag phase was observed in its degradation,
427 suggesting the presence of a well-established population of microorganisms capable of
428 producing the ether cleaving enzymes for the uptake of this glycol ether. Regarding the
429 SMA assay for the mixture, different slopes in the methane production during the
430 degradation of the three compounds were not observed; i.e., a constant SMA was
431 observed during the whole test, and similar values of SMA as those observed for the
432 more biodegradable solvents were achieved.

433 3.5 Microbial community analysis

434 Fig. 6 shows the DGGE banding patterns for the bacterial (Fig. 6a) and archaeal (Fig.
435 6b) populations of the sample taken from the inoculum and the samples taken from the
436 three UASB reactors at days 37, 89, 131 and 169 of the operation. The bands indicated
437 in Fig. 6 were excised and sequenced. Table 5 summarizes their designation, the level of
438 similarity to related GenBank sequences and the phylogenetic affiliations of each strain.

439 A total of seventeen predominant bands were excised from the bacterial DGGE (Fig.
440 6a): four corresponding to the seed sludge and thirteen to the UASB reactors. The
441 DGGE pattern showed a shift in the bacterial populations of the reactors relative to the
442 inoculum, and only one of the bands observed initially (B7) remained in the three
443 reactors throughout the experiment. This shift was related to the different operational
444 and environmental conditions of our experiment compared to those applied in the
445 anaerobic digester source of the seed sludge.

446 Bands B7 and B16 were identified as *Geobacter psychrophilus* and *Geobacter*
447 *chapelleyi*, respectively. These microorganisms, which were present in all three reactors,
448 can oxidize substrates such as ethanol, acetate, formate or lactate, coupled with the
449 reduction of iron or manganese oxides (Coates et al., 2001; Nevin et al., 2005).
450 *Geobacter* species are known to be specialists in making electrical connections with
451 extracellular electron acceptors and other organisms, such as *Methanosaeta*, based on
452 the direct interspecies electron transfer (DIET) mechanism (Shen et al., 2016). Band
453 B10 was affiliated with *Pelobacter propionicus*. This microorganism has been reported
454 to produce acetate and propionate from ethanol (Schink et al., 1987) and has been found
455 to be involved in the syntrophic oxidation of primary alcohols and diols with hydrogen-
456 utilizing partners via the interspecies H₂ transfer mechanism (Shen et al., 2016). Band

457 B11 was associated with *Smithella propionica*, which is a species of syntrophic
458 propionate-oxidizing bacteria that produces small amounts of butyrate with H₂ or
459 formate-using methanogenic partners in addition to acetate (Liu et al., 1999). These
460 bacteria, which are involved in the syntrophic production and consumption of VFA,
461 were not observed in the seed sludge, but their intensity (especially B10) became
462 stronger in the three reactors once the granulation process had progressed, being
463 observed earlier in the reactors with chitosan.

464 Band B12 was related to *Treponema caldarium*. These bacteria are possibly
465 homoacetogens, which are able to consume H₂ and CO₂ to produce acetate (Zhang et
466 al., 2009). The intensity of this band was very low compared to those of the *Pelobacter*
467 and *Smithella*, which suggests that the H₂ produced in our reactors was mainly utilized
468 in syntrophic associations with hydrogenotrophic methanogens.

469 The phylum *Firmicutes* was represented by bands B8 and B15. The first band was
470 related to *Clostridium* sp., which are commonly present in methanogenic environments
471 (Díaz et al., 2006). Band B15 was affiliated with *Trichococcus pasteurii*, an aerotolerant
472 fermentative organism growing with glucose, sucrose and lactose to produce lactate,
473 acetate, formate and other acids, which has previously been found in anaerobic
474 bioreactors operated at low temperature (Bialek et al., 2014). Although the intensity of
475 band B15 was low throughout the experiment, it could have been favored due to the
476 operational temperature established ($24.0 \pm 1.4^\circ\text{C}$). The bands corresponding to the
477 phylum *Bacteroidetes* were related to the genus *Capnocytophaga* (B9, B13 and B17)
478 and *Flavobacterium* (B14). These microorganisms are facultative anaerobes. They have
479 been previously found in anaerobic reactors treating acidogenic substrates or municipal
480 sludge (Li et al., 2016; Maspolim et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2016).

481 Regarding the archaeal community, a total of nine bands were excised and identified
482 (Fig. 6b and Table 5). Some differences were observed between the control reactor and
483 those inoculated with chitosan, which could explain how the polymer accelerated the
484 granulation process. Although almost all the bands identified in the inoculum remained
485 in all samples throughout the experiment, it is remarkable that bands A3 and A5 were
486 not observed on day 37 in R1, while in the reactors inoculated with chitosan, these
487 bands were present. Bands A3 and A5 are closely related to the *Methanosaeta* species.
488 *Methanosaeta* is a well-known acetotrophic methanogen described as a key
489 microorganism in the granulation processes in which it acts as a nucleation center
490 (Macleod et al., 1990). It seems that chitosan can help retain these microorganisms, as
491 Khemkao et al. (2011) observed while treating palm oil mill wastewater in an UASB
492 reactor to which chitosan had been added at the start-up. Therefore, the higher
493 population of acetotrophic methanogens could explain the improved performance of the
494 reactors that were inoculated with chitosan. As previously indicated, several studies
495 have found that DIET can occur between *Geobacter* and *Methanosaeta* species within
496 aggregates from anaerobic reactors treating wastewaters with a high content of ethanol,
497 such as brewery wastewaters (Morita et al., 2011; Rotaru et al., 2014; Shrestha et al.,
498 2014). Therefore, it could be assumed that DIET interactions were present in the
499 aggregates from our reactors, since ethanol was the main solvent in the synthetic
500 wastewater we applied as well as an intermediate in the degradation of ethyl acetate and
501 1-ethoxy-2-propanol, which were the other solvents in the reactors feeding stream.

502 The predominant band found in the archaeal DGGE in all biomass samples during the
503 experiment was band A1, which was identified as *Methanocorpusculum labreanum*, a
504 hydrogenotrophic archaea related to the granulation process in high-rate anaerobic
505 reactors operating at a low temperature (O'Reilly et al., 2009). The operation of our

506 reactors at sub-mesophilic temperatures favored the prevalence of this organism, which
507 increased in abundance from day 37 until the end of the experiment. Band A2 was
508 identified as *Methanospirillum hungatei*, which is a hydrogenotrophic methanogen
509 associated with *Pelobacter* bacteria in the syntrophic degradation of primary alcohols
510 and diols (Eichler and Schink, 1985). This band was present in the inoculum but was
511 not observed in any reactor at any other time, despite the fact that ethanol was the main
512 solvent in the feeding synthetic wastewater and *Pelobacter* was observed throughout the
513 experiment in all the reactors. The operational conditions and the predominance of other
514 hydrogen-utilizing microorganisms belonging to the *Methanomicrobiales* order, such as
515 *Methanoscorgulum*, could limit the growth of the *Methanospirillum* species.

516 The order *Methanobacteriales* was represented by *Methanobacterium beijingense* (A6).
517 This hydrogenotrophic archaea was detected in all reactors from day 89 onwards. Its
518 abundance remained stable, according to the intensity of the bands, until the end of the
519 trial. *Methanobacterium beijingense* was isolated from an anaerobic digester for the
520 treatment of beer-manufacture wastewater (Ma et al., 2005) and has been found in
521 anaerobic reactors treating organic solvents in phenol or trichloroethylene-contaminated
522 wastewater at a broad range of temperatures (15 to 37°C; Chen et al., 2008; Siggins et
523 al., 2011). Band A7 was closely related to *Methanosarcina mazei*. This acetoclastic
524 methanogen could compete with *Methanosaeta* depending on the acetate concentration,
525 being predominant at high concentrations (Conklin et al., 2006; McMahon et al., 2001;
526 Wiegant, 1987). *Methanosarcina mazei* was only identified on day 89 in the control
527 reactor, but it was not observed afterwards. Although the control reactor had eventual
528 peaks of VFA during phase III, the average VFA concentration remained below 200 mg
529 HAc L⁻¹, thus favoring the dominance of *Methanosaeta* over *Methanosarcina*.

530 The biomass sample taken from the inoculum and the granular samples taken from the
531 three UASB reactors at day 169 were analyzed by high-throughput sequencing. A
532 summary of the microbial community structure at phylum level is plotted in Fig. Sup4.
533 The dominant phyla detected in relative abundances higher than 1% of total sequences
534 in at least one sample include *Euryarchaeota*, *Actinobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes*,
535 *Chloroflexi*, *Firmicutes*, *Proteobacteria*, *Synergistetes* and *Cloacimonetes*. Results show
536 a shift in the microbial communities from the inoculum to the granular sludge of the
537 three UASB reactors throughout the operation. The microbial communities observed in
538 all reactors at day 169 are quite similar as same wastewater composition was used. The
539 *Euryarchaeota* phylum that includes the methanogenic microorganisms became highly
540 dominant in the granular samples. This phylum increases its relative abundance from a
541 value of 0.31% in the inoculum to values in the chitosan-assisted reactors, R2 and R3,
542 of 32.39% and 33.60%, respectively, with greater abundances than that obtained in the
543 control reactor, 29.90%. Other dominant phyla as *Firmicutes* decreased the relative
544 abundance during the course of the experiment in all reactors, whereas *Proteobacteria*
545 increased the abundance. *Actinobacteria* and *Chloroflexi* phylum, with percentage
546 greater than 5% in the inoculum, almost disappeared in the three reactors throughout the
547 operation. The relative abundance of the dominant genera (with a relative abundance
548 higher than 0.1% at least in one sample) is presented in Fig. 7. Several genera related to
549 bacteria as *Coprothermobacter*, *Clostridium*, *Anaerobaculum* and W5 with relative
550 abundances of 5.1%, 1.3%, 3.0% and 6.3%, respectively, in the initial biomass almost
551 disappeared at day 169; whereas other bacteria genera grew in the same period reaching
552 significant abundance in the three reactors. For example, *Geobacter* genus had an
553 abundance ranging between 4.1 and 7.3% in the granular samples while in the inoculum
554 the abundance was 0.2%. The genus *Syntrophus* also increased the abundance until

555 values within 1–3.4% from a value lower than 0.1% in the inoculum. This genus,
556 detected by high-throughput sequencing, belongs to *Syntrophaceae* family as same as
557 genus *Smithella* (detected by DGGE). *Pelobacter* genus was also detected in the three
558 reactors. These genera are associated to syntrophic communities of bacteria and
559 methanogenic archaea. The importance of syntrophic communities in high-rate
560 methanogenic reactors has been pointed out by Stams et al. (2012), who have indicated
561 that aggregation reduces the distance between the bacteria and methanogens favoring
562 the transfer of metabolites, which is essential to achieve high conversion rates. The
563 archaeal communities of the inoculum and the three reactors on day 169 matched those
564 obtained from DGGE. They were composed mainly with four genera:
565 *Methanobacterium*, *Methanobrevibacter*, *Methanocorpusculum* and *Methanosaeta*, with
566 an increase in their relative abundance in the granules in comparison with the inoculum.
567 The *Methanocorpusculum* was the most abundant genus in the granular sludge with
568 values of 25.3%, 30.1% and 31.7% in R1, R2 and R3, respectively. The other archaea
569 genera reached values within 0.5-1.5% in all reactors.

570 Recently, Bravo et al. (2017) reported that *Methanosaeta*, together with
571 *Methanospirillum* and *Methanobacterium*, were the predominant species in granules
572 from a pilot EGSB reactor treating industrial solvent wastewater with a similar
573 composition to that of the synthetic wastewater employed in this study. In our reactors,
574 the *Methanocorpusculum*, *Methanobacterium* and *Methanosaeta* species were found to
575 be the predominant archaea. Since the first microorganism was present in the inoculum
576 and its abundance remained throughout the study, it can be inferred that the origin of the
577 biomass source, as well as the environmental and operational conditions applied during
578 the experiment, could influence significantly the microbial community established for
579 the degradation of similar substrates.

580

581 4 Conclusion

582 In this study, three UASB reactors treating wastewater polluted with ethanol, ethyl
583 acetate and 1-ethoxy-2-propanol were successfully operated. The following main
584 conclusions can be obtained.

- 585 • Chitosan addition improved the start-up and the overall performance of the
586 UASB reactors inoculated with flocculent anaerobic sludge and operated up to
587 an OLR of $20 \text{ kg COD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$. The chitosan-assisted reactors achieved removal
588 efficiencies $>92\%$ in only 11 days and showed more stable behavior.
- 589 • The solvent 1-ethoxy-2-propanol was successfully degraded, although with
590 significantly lower SMA value in comparison with ethanol and ethyl acetate.
- 591 • Granulation was successfully achieved in a shorter time in the UASB reactors
592 supplied with chitosan with larger granules appearing earlier. The granules of
593 the chitosan-assisted reactors exhibited better settling velocities ($>35 \text{ m h}^{-1}$),
594 higher methanogenic activities and higher content of EPS.
- 595 • DGEE and high-throughput sequencing results showed the shift of microbial
596 community to increase the relative abundance of Archaea. After 169 days, the
597 three reactors presented similar microbial community due to the treatment of the
598 same solvents. *Geobacter* and *Methanocorpusculum* were the dominant genera
599 of the microbial community degrading anaerobically ethanol, ethyl acetate and
600 1-ethoxy-2-propanol.

601

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611

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- 839
- 840

841 **Table 1.** Operational parameters of UASB reactors during the granulation experiment.

Operational day	Phase I			Phase II			Phase III		
	0 – 22			23 – 89			90 – 219		
	R1	R2	R3	R1	R2	R3	R1	R2	R3
OLR (kg COD m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)	0.3 – 0.6	0.3 – 0.6	0.3 – 0.6	2.3	2.3	4	2.3 – 20	2.3 – 20	4 – 20
Influent COD (g L ⁻¹)	2.3 – 4.5	2.3 – 4.5	2.3 – 4.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	5.0 – 7.6	5.0 – 7.6	4.0 – 5.3
Influent E2P (mg L ⁻¹)	110 – 220	110 – 220	110 – 220	145	145	145	240 – 370	240 – 370	190 – 260
u (m h ⁻¹)	1	1	0.1	1	1	0.1	0.1 – 0.2	0.1 – 0.2	0.1 – 0.2

842

843 **Table 2.** Percentage of particles larger than 300 μm (consider as granules) over time in
 844 all reactors.

		Operational time (day)												
		Phase I		Phase II			Phase III							
		0	22	23	54	89	90	112	131	169	190	219		
Granules (%)	R1	1 st Chitosan Addition	Rec. ON	0.3	3.0		4.9	4.9	Recirculation OFF	4.9	18.1	25.4	33.0	42.0
	R2			0.3	4.0		6.3	8.5		22.7	25.0	40.2	56.4	54.0
	R3			0.3	6.8	2 nd Chitosan Addition	22.2	21.9		24.5	30.1	57.3	65.7	64.7

845
 846
 847

848 **Table 3.** Extracellular polymer content of the sludge samples from the reactors during
 849 the study.
 850

	EPS (mg g VSS ⁻¹)	Polysaccharides			Proteins			Total EPS		
	Day	R1	R2	R3	R1	R2	R3	R1	R2	R3
Phase I	0	5.7	5.7	5.7	2.4	2.4	2.4	8.1	8.1	8.1
	18	1.4	9.5	2.2	2.3	3.9	4.2	3.8	13.4	6.3
Phase II	54	16.0	14.5	17.2	14.0	40.9	36.8	30.0	55.3	54.0
	89	2.6	4.0	9.2	26.5	49.7	37.4	29.1	53.7	46.5
Phase III	112	7.1	8.2	4.1	19.1	48.4	30.3	26.2	56.6	34.3
	131	7.7	19.8	10.8	49.2	44.8	55.6	56.9	64.6	66.4
	190	8.3	21.1	30.4	81.3	101.9	168.3	89.5	123.0	198.7
	219	11.2	24.0	20.7	94.2	158.2	131.3	105.5	182.3	152.0

851

852 **Table 4.** SMA of the granular sludge of each reactor after 219 days of operation.

	SMA (NmL CH ₄ g VSS ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)			
	Ethanol	Ethyl Acetate	E2P	Mixture
R1: Control	277.8 ± 8.0	265.5 ± 22.4	66.7 ± 5.2	245.2 ± 3.0
R2	434.5 ± 2.4	370.0 ± 14.0	73.3 ± 2.2	390.7 ± 4.6
R3	488.6 ± 4.1	386.9 ± 16.0	79.9 ± 1.9	439.9 ± 1.9

853

854 **Table 5.** Phylogenic affiliation of bacterial and archaeal sequenced bands from DGGE
 855 profiles (Fig. 6).

DGGE band	Closest organism (accession. version number)	Similarity %	Phylogenetic group (phylum/order)
B1	<i>Paludibaculum fermentans</i> (NR_134120.1)	95	Bacteroidetes/Bacteroidales
B2	<i>Catalinimonas niigatensis</i> (NR_133994.1)	92	Acidobacteria
B3	<i>Hydrogenophaga luteola</i> (NR_145548.1)	100	Proteobacteria/Burkholderiales
B4	<i>Desulfoviregula thermocuniculi</i> (NR_043640.1)	88	Firmicutes/Thermoanaerobacteriales
B5	<i>Capnocytophaga cynodegmi</i> (NR_043063.1)	94	Bacteroidetes/Flavobacteriales
B6	<i>Flavobacterium aquaticum</i> (NR_108893.1)	96	Bacteroidetes/Flavobacteriales
B7	<i>Geobacter psychrophilus</i> (NR_043075.1)	95	Proteobacteria/Desulfuromonadales
B8	<i>Clostridium limosum</i> (NR_104825.1)	90	Firmicutes/Clostridiales
B9	<i>Capnocytophaga sputigena</i> (NR_113564.1)	88	Bacteroidetes/Flavobacteriales
B10	<i>Pelobacter propionicus</i> (NR_074975.1)	93	Proteobacteria/Desulfuromonadales
B11	<i>Smithella propionica</i> (NR_024989.1)	92	Proteobacteria/Syntrophobacteriales
B12	<i>Treponema caldarium</i> (NR_074757.1)	91	Spirochaetes/Spirochaetales
B13	<i>Capnocytophaga granulosa</i> (NR_044777.1)	92	Bacteroidetes/Flavobacteriales
B14	<i>Flavobacterium branchiicola</i> (NR_145953.1)	85	Bacteroidetes/Flavobacteriales
B15	<i>Trichococcus pasteurii</i> (NR_036793.2)	98	Firmicutes/Lactobacillales
B16	<i>Geobacter chapellei</i> (NR_025982.1)	95	Proteobacteria/Desulfuromonadales
B17	<i>Capnocytophaga granulosa</i> (NR_044777.1)	92	Bacteroidetes/Flavobacteriales
A1	<i>Methanocorpusculum labreanum</i> (NR_074173.1)	100	Methanomicrobiales/Methanocorpusculaceae
A2	<i>Methanospirillum hungatei</i> (NR_074177.1)	79	Methanomicrobiales/Methanospirillaceae
A3	<i>Methanosaeta concilii</i> (NR_102903.1)	100	Methanosarcinales/Methanosaetaceae
A4	<i>Methanosaeta thermophila</i> (NR_074214.1)	96	Methanosarcinales/Methanosaetaceae
A5	<i>Methanosaeta harundinacea</i> (NR_043203.1)	99	Methanosarcinales/Methanosaetaceae
A6	<i>Methanobacterium beijingense</i> (NR_028202.1)	99	Methanobacteriales/Methanobacteriaceae
A7	<i>Methanosarcina mazei</i> (NR_041956.1)	100	Methanosarcinales/Methanosarcinaceae
A8	<i>Methanosaeta harundinacea</i> (NR_043203.1)	98	Methanosarcinales/Methanosaetaceae
A9	<i>Methanosaeta concilii</i> (NR_102903.1)	100	Methanosarcinales/Methanosaetaceae

856

857 **Figure captions**

858

859 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagram of experimental set-up.

860

861 **Figure 2. a)** Applied Organic Loading Rate (**—**) and COD removal efficiency
862 (**●,○,▲**) of the reactors during the experiment. **b)** VFA concentration in the effluent of
863 the reactors.

864

865 **Figure 3.** Variation of the applied E2P Organic Loading Rate (**—**) and E2P removal
866 efficiency (**●,○,▲**) of the reactors with time.

867

868 **Figure 4.** Evolution of the particle size and distribution over time in all reactors.

869

870 **Figure 5.** SEM images: Morphology of the granules after 219 days. **a.** Control reactor
871 (R1), **b.** chitosan-assisted reactor (R3), **c.** Magnification of granules in R1, **d.**
872 Magnification of granules in R3.

873

874 **Figure 6.** Variation with time of the DGGE profiles of biomass samples from the three
875 reactors. a) Bacterial DGGE profiles, b) Archeal DGGE profiles.

876

877 **Figure 7.** Heatmap distribution of the most abundant genera (relative abundance > 0.1%
878 at least in one sample) of biomass samples from the inoculum and the three reactors.

Figure 1

Figure4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Supplementary material

Equations to calculate RE_{COD} and RE_{E2P} :

1- The COD removal efficiency was calculated as follows:

$$RE_{COD} (\%) = 1 - \frac{COD_{effluent}}{COD_{influent}}$$

where $COD_{effluent}$, is soluble COD concentration, measured according to Standard Methods, and $COD_{influent}$, is the COD concentration in the influent, calculated according to the injected mass rate ($g\ d^{-1}$) and the composition of the mixture of ethanol, ethyl acetate and 1-ethoxy-2 propanol, using their respective theoretical factors for the conversion from $g\ L^{-1}$ to $g\ COD\ L^{-1}$ ($2.08\ g\ COD\ g\ Ethanol^{-1}$, $1.82\ g\ COD\ g\ Ethyl\ Acetate^{-1}$ and $2.15\ g\ COD\ g\ E2P^{-1}$), and the wastewater volumetric flowrate fed ($L\ d^{-1}$).

2- The removal efficiency of the solvent E2P was calculated as follows:

$$RE_{E2P} (\%) = 1 - \frac{C_{E2P,effluent}}{C_{E2P,influent}}$$

being $C_{E2P,effluent}$, the concentration of the solvent as $g\ E2P\ L^{-1}$, which was measured by gas chromatography (as explained in Materials and Methods), and $C_{E2P,influent}$ ($g\ E2P\ L^{-1}$), the concentration of E2P in the influent calculated by the mass rate injected of E2P ($g\ E2P\ d^{-1}$) and the wastewater volumetric flowrate fed ($L\ d^{-1}$).

Table Sup1. Macro- and micro-nutrients supplementation.

Macro-nutrients	mg g COD ⁻¹	Micro-nutrients	mg g COD ⁻¹
NH ₄ Cl	25.5	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	0.42
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	14.2	H ₃ BO ₃	0.11
KCl	2.4	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.01
Yeast extract	7.5	CuCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.01
Mg ⁺² as MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	40 mg Mg L ⁻¹	MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.14
Ca ⁺² as CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	150 mg Ca L ⁻¹	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.06
		Al ₂ O ₃	0.06
		CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.16
		NiSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	0.04
		EDTANa ₂	0.1

Figure Sup1. Variations in the turbidity and sludge volume index (SVI) at different doses of chitosan applied to the inoculum.

Figure Sup2. Changes of the operational parameters over time in the three UASB reactors during the granulation experiment.

Figure Sup3. Variations in the percentage of granules (particles >300μm) with the protein-ECP content in the three reactors.

Figure Sup4. Microbial distribution at phylum-level of the inoculum and the samples of the three UASB at day 169.